

Mapping forest assortment at parcel level to support wood mobilization

Introduction

Efficiently categorizing wood assortments is a critical task for gaining a more precise understanding of the genuine value of wood, whether it's within a forest or stored in a yard. Additionally, it's essential to measure and classify wood assortments at the parcel level before harvesting to obtain accurate insights into the forest's overall value.

Within the GO-SURF system, various maps, such as the Growing Stock Volume Map and Forest Types Map developed using decision support tools, enable the creation of a map that identifies potential wood assortments. This map employs the regional mean value to extract this valuable information. At the forest parcel level, the map provides the percentage of growing stock volume for each potential wood assortment, such as pellets, wood chips, firewood, poles and beams.

This map is a valuable tool for forest managers in assessing the economic value of the forest prior to its sale. Furthermore, it is integrated into the Decision Support System within the OG-SURF framework, making it accessible through a simple polygon design in the user interface.

Lessons learned

The map of wood assortments provides information at parcel level and from the point of view of forest managers working within the project appears to be a support instrument to quantify the possible value of the forest. However, in our study area there are many forests managed as coppices so the main forest assortments that were observed in our map were mainly firwood and chips.

For further information contact

Francesca Giannetti, Assistant Professor, University of Florence, Italy, e-mail: francesca.giannetti@unifi.it

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.go-surf.it/>

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